

Effectiveness of digital educational interventions in promoting influenza vaccination among adults aged 50 years or older: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Effectiveness of digital educational interventions in promoting influenza vaccination among adults aged 50 years or older: a systematic review and meta-analysis

Condition or domain being studied

Influenza Virus Vaccine; Digital health intervention; Older Adult Care; Middle Aged

Rationale for the review

Seasonal influenza remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, with adults aged 50 years or above experiencing a disproportionately high burden of severe disease and complications. Although influenza vaccination is an effective preventive measure, vaccination uptake in this age group remains suboptimal in many settings. Traditional, in-person health education strategies face increasing constraints related to workforce capacity, cost, and accessibility, highlighting the need for scalable and efficient alternatives.

Digital educational interventions, such as web-based platforms, mobile applications, text messaging, videos, and chatbot-based tools, have emerged as promising approaches to improve vaccine-related knowledge, attitudes, and uptake. While a growing number of randomized controlled trials have evaluated such interventions for influenza vaccination, the evidence has not been comprehensively synthesized, and the magnitude and consistency of their effects among adults aged 50 years or above remain unclear. In particular, it is uncertain whether intervention effectiveness differs between adults aged 50–64 years and those aged 65 years or older, who may have distinct health needs, risk perceptions, and access to vaccination services.

This systematic review and meta-analysis aims to synthesize randomized controlled trial evidence on the effectiveness of digital educational interventions in promoting seasonal influenza vaccination among adults aged 50 years or above. By quantifying pooled effects and examining age-based subgroup differences, this review seeks to provide robust, policy-relevant evidence to inform the design and implementation of digital vaccination promotion strategies for middle-aged and older adult populations, thereby addressing an important gap in the existing literature.

Review objectives

This systematic review and meta-analysis aims to synthesize randomized controlled trial evidence on the effectiveness of digital educational interventions in promoting influenza vaccination among adults aged 50 years or above

Keywords

Digital interventions; Influenza vaccine; Systematic review and meta-analysis; People aged 50 and over

Country

China

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Included

Adults aged 50 years or above.

Excluded

Studies not involving people (e.g., laboratory simulations, clinician-only samples).

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Included

Digital health intervention

Use of digital educational interventions to promote influenza vaccination uptake. Digital educational interventions are defined as interventions intended to change vaccination-related behaviors, delivered via digital or mobile devices directly to participants, including text-message-based education (text, video, or audio messages), internet-delivered interventions (e.g., websites, mobile applications, social media platforms, chatbot/ChatGPT) and other interactive or non-interactive digital educational strategies

Excluded

Studies without any digital educational intervention component.

Studies focusing solely on vaccine immunogenicity or effectiveness, clinical outcomes of influenza infection, and economic evaluations (e.g., cost-effectiveness) without behavioral or perceptual components.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

This review does not have any comparators

Study design

Only randomized study types will be included.

Excluded

Observational studies (e.g., cross-sectional, cohort and case-control)

Reviews, narratives, commentaries, or editorials

Dissertations, preprints, government reports, newspaper articles, textbooks, book chapters, and protocols

Laboratory studies, model and framework studies, and validation studies

Gray literature (e.g., conference abstracts, policy reports, preprints)

Context

Studies that reported quantitative measures of influenza vaccination uptake, intention or attitudes will be included.

TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

20 January 2026

Review timeline

Start date: 5 January 2026. End date: 18 February 2026.

Date of registration in PROSPERO

20 January 2026

AVAILABILITY OF FULL PROTOCOL

Availability of full protocol

A full protocol has not been written.

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Search for unpublished studies

Only published studies will be sought.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched

The main databases to be searched are *CINAHL - Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature*, *Embase - Embase via Ovid*, *MEDLINE*, *PsycInfo*, *PubMed* and *Scopus*.

Other important or specialist databases that will be searched

Web of Science; Global Health; Cochrane Library; APA PsyArticle

Search language restrictions

The review will only include studies published in English.

Search date restrictions

There are no search date restrictions.

Other methods of identifying studies

No other methods will be used.

Link to search strategy

A full search strategy has been uploaded to PROSPERO. The PDF may be accessed through this link <https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/d6df1b7e5ee4f6ef75f9a130f6535111.pdf>.

Selection process

Studies will be screened independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Other relevant information about searching and screening

We systematically searched PubMed, MEDLINE, Embase, Web of Science, Global Health, CINAHL, Cochrane Library, APA PsycINFO, and APA PsycArticles for studies, without restrictions on country or setting. The search strategy was developed according to the PICOS framework: participants (adults aged 50 years or above), intervention (digital educational interventions), comparison (none), outcomes (quantitative measures of influenza vaccination uptake, intention or attitudes), and study design (randomized controlled trials). Boolean operators ("OR" and "AND") were applied to combine keywords and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms related to digital education interventions, influenza vaccination outcomes, and people aged 50 or above.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction from published articles and reports

Data will be extracted independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Authors will not be contacted for further information.

Study risk of bias or quality assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using: *Cochrane RoB-2*

Data will be assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Additional information will be sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports.

Reporting bias assessment

We will use the RoB 2 tool to include a domain on "selection of the reported result", which directly addresses whether the results are selectively reported or missing.

Certainty assessment

Certainty of findings will not be assessed

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

Quantitative measures of influenza vaccination uptake, intention or attitudes

Additional outcomes

Not applicable

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

We will perform meta-analyses using random-effects models to pool data and calculate standardized mean differences (SMDs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for RCTs. Hedge's g will be used to estimate the SMDs to remove bias due to the varying sample sizes of the included studies. Statistical significance will be set at $p < 0.05$, and SMD values will be interpreted using conventional thresholds: trivial (0.00–0.19), small (0.20–0.49), medium (0.50–0.79), or large (≥ 0.80).

Sensitivity analyses will be conducted by sequentially excluding individual studies. Subgroup analyses will be explored potential effect modifiers, including age (50–64 vs 65 years older), intervention duration (< 6 vs ≥ 6 months), outcome measurement (self-reported vs objective).

Between-study heterogeneity will be assessed using the Q test ($p < 0.05$ indicating significance) and quantified with I^2 statistics (small $< 25\%$, moderate 25–75%, large $> 75\%$). Publication bias will be evaluated through funnel plot inspection and Egger's test.

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work	✓	✓
Formal searching/study identification	✓	
Screening search results against inclusion criteria	✓	
Data extraction or receipt of IPD		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

Publication of review results

Results of the review will be published in English.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

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No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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Funding source

Review has no specific/external funding but is supported by guarantor/review team (non-commercial) institutions.

Peer review

There has been no peer review of this planned review.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This review will be conducted according to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines.

Review conflict of interest

Declared individual interests are recorded under team member details.. No additional interests are recorded for this review.

Medical Subject Headings

Clinical Trial; Digital Technology; Influenza Vaccines

SIMILAR REVIEWS

Check for similar records already in PROSPERO

PROSPERO identified a number of existing PROSPERO records that were similar to this one (last check made on 20 January 2026). These are shown below along with the reasons given by that the review team for the reviews being different and/or proceeding.

- Effectiveness of the MF59-Adjuvanted Trivalent or Quadrivalent Seasonal Influenza Vaccine (FLUAD) Among Adults Aged 65 or Older, a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis [published 23 July 2020] [CRD42020177747]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Health economic evaluations of vaccination strategies in adults aged 65 years old and older: a systematic review [published 18 October 2024] [CRD42024598549]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Effectiveness of social prescribing interventions in promoting quality of life among older adults: a systematic review protocol [published 27 April 2025] [CRD420251007313]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Parental Acceptance, Parental Hesitancy, and Uptake of Seasonal Influenza Vaccination among Children Aged 6-59 Months: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 3 June 2023] [CRD42023428862]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

- Literature review of the rates of hospitalization and mortality associated with laboratory confirmed influenza in adults aged 50-64 years [published 3 July 2021] [CRD42021250308]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- What is the effect of deprivation on outcomes post-fragility fracture in adults aged 50 years or older? [published 2 February 2016] [CRD42016033840]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

PROSPERO version history

- [Version 1.0, published 20 Jan 2026](#)

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